

ON SOME ETHNIC HOUSING AREAS OF CĂLĂRAȘI

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ABSTRACT. The paper makes a general description of poverty areas inhabited by Roma communities in Călărași, Romania and tries to put them into a general context of urban geography. In particular it aims to illustrate the urban setting, the housing conditions of the dwellers, the dynamics and the formation of three ethnic and poverty enclaves that display to a various degree the characters of an urban ghetto (Oborul Nou, Doi Moldoveni and Livadă) using mainly first-hand accounts of the inhabitants, analyzing the spatial policies of the authorities and the ways in which people deal with territory and housing issues. The analysis highlights the specificities of spatialization of Roma communities and racialization of poverty in small size Romanian cities, where segregation policies are rarely explicit, physical distances are less relevant, but the spatial exclusion process is no less visible and defined rather by substandard infrastructure, poor access and unfriendly limits.

Keywords: urban geography, slum areas, Roma communities, housing deprivation

Urban geography²

Territorial, Historical and Urban Context

Călărași is the capital city of the Călărași County and it is situated in the South Eastern part of the Romanian Plain (Cîmpia Română), more precisely the Bărăganului Ialomiței, a major agricultural domain, stretching about 150 km along the North bank of the Danube. The two main *municipia* of the county, Oltenița and Călărași, both situated along the river, are the major landmarks of the border with Bulgaria for this sector of the river and place Călărași in an important geographical inflexion point that marks the entrance of Danube on the Romanian territory and the line of separation between Wallachia and Dobrudja, the presence of the Turkish Roma in the region having to do with this historical heritage. The city is situated

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² The article was completed within the research "Spatialization and racialization of social exclusion. The social and cultural formation of 'Gypsy ghettos' in Romania in a European context" (www.sparex-ro.eu), supported by a grant of the Romanian National Authority for Scientific Research, CNCS – UEFISCDI, project number PN-II-ID-PCE-2011-3-0354.

on a secondary branch of the Danube named Borcea and dominates both a vast flooding area and a huge agricultural territory, the abundance of food resources and the geographical and morphological situation that allows for the development of a relatively large size port being strong determinants in regards with the huge investment programmes that took place here in the late communist years. Many of these developments were never fully finished and their abandonment has now major consequences not only in economical but in territorial terms as well; the industrial belt of the city, largely abandoned, matching the area of the city itself.

Though relatively small in demographic terms the city has, and it always had, a significant importance as a transit point to the Balkans, the very name of the city originating from „călărășii ștafetari”, the couriers that were delivering messages to Istanbul and for whom this was an important station (Știucă, 2006). The connection is done by ferryboat to Silistra, Bulgaria but recent plans, launched during the last electoral campaign are planning for a bridge over the Danube.

Fig. 1. Călărăși county map.

Source: Google Maps.³

³ http://www.google.co.uk/imgres?imgurl=http://i127.photobucket.com/albums/p138/bobesman/rutiere/-Harta-judet-Calarasi.jpg&imgrefurl=http://cristi70.3xforum.ro/post/4313/1/Meteo_Calarasi_Live_webcam_Calarasi_Harta_rutiera_Calarasi/&h=1138&w=1626&sz=385&tbnid=7ABSquxpzkSdhM:&tbnh=84&tbnw=120&prev=/search%3Fq%3Djudetul%2Bcalarasi%2Bharta%26tbm%3Dsch%26tbo%3Du&zoom=1&q=judetul+calarasi+harta&usq=_TQ8X45jblYJfWPuBOKNt_OJAg=&docid=Wam1sYCNDRiwM&hl=en&sa=X&ei=Obx_UYOuM-eu4ASz3IHACw&ved=0CDkQ9QEwAg&dur=1020

The relatively long distance to Bucharest, around 130 km, is no obstacle for an intense relation with the capital city, many inhabitants commuting daily to the capital for various reasons. The connection is even better now through the highway to Constanța and it is likely to change the direction of the development of the city. The very weak development of the settlements situated in the hinterland of Bucharest places the capital in a hegemonic position, being able to draw resources from a vast territory composed of agricultural land where people live in small villages and are a constant source of cheap work force. This major misbalance is responsible for the weak territorial cohesion of the southern territories and for a lack of polycentric network in the area. Despite the fact that Călărași is the capital of the county its cultural, economic and political importance is much smaller than of the cities situated at the North and West of Bucharest and it actually marks the limit of territorial influence of Bucharest. In the particular case of Călărași there is a historical explanation, the city itself being until 1852 in the property of the important Bucharest based Colțea Monastery, from which the citizens bought it by public subscription. The emancipation episode was followed by major urbanistic interventions that still give the eclectic character of the centre: large boulevards with relatively large plots of land on which you can still find stylish houses with small beautiful gardens that belonged to the local merchants, public buildings of a modest scale but carefully placed in order to define a small city with a distinct personality and a strong option for an emerging modernity.

A different layer was added during the forced industrialization era and that led to the creation of mass housing and densification in a typical socialist city scenario which culminated with the creation of a Civic Centre, part of the late 80's campaign initiated by Ceaușescu but here with a less devastating impact on the historical core.

The rapport with the neighbouring villages evolved in time in the sense of an incomplete assimilation of former rural areas which led to a particularly elongated shape of the city, built on two main roads from East to West, which now starts and ends with quite long areas that are still characterized by low density and lack of urban equipment. There is a recent, incomplete development towards North, which is now the major connection with the highway and that will probably become more important in the near future. One of our study areas, Oborul Nou is situated in that direction and their relocation has to do with this major change of the direction of the development of the city.

The brownfields are located both North and South and equal or even exceed the territory of the city determining a particular geography of access, the East penetration being guarded by several kilometres of spectacular industrial ruins. Some of our areas are directly connected with this form of strong division between the suburbs, or the edges of the residential areas and the abandoned sites.

Fig. 2. Călărași –Siderca, the company that was supposed to be the largest steel factory of Europe at its time and for which a port was built, was never completed and now guards the exit road to Bucharest for about two kilometres. Demolition works took place in the last twenty years and are still ongoing.

Source: Author's photo.

Demography

The last census of 2011 confirms an accelerated descending trend, Călărași having now 57.000 inhabitants⁴, 19% less than in 2002 when the 70.000 inhabitants were still 10% less than the 77.000 of 1992. The decrease has a strong logic if we are to follow the date for the previous twenty years before 1989 as for 1977, which was before the humongous industrial development programmes, the city barely reached 50.000 inhabitants. Since the demographic raise was based on the migration of industrial workers it is only logical that the dramatic restraint of the industrial capacities of the city would lead to a reverse of the phenomenon. This has a lot to do with two of the areas we surveyed, typical urban ghettos formed in former worker's dormitories that were either sold to the inhabitants or transformed into social housing and that are now struggling with huge rates of unemployment, disconnected from utility services, overcrowded and facing insecurity and violence issues. Self declared Roma are just 2051 and the Turks are 412. According to estimates made by local Roma experts the real figures are much higher.

Urban ghettos

The way different actors name, or refuse to give a name to these areas tells a lot about how these territories are represented in the collective imagery

⁴ The census took place in 2011 and the results were published in 2012 but a recent correction from 2013 counts 65181 permanent inhabitants. The extra figure of 8500 persons might indicate the ones involved in the circular migration that is characteristic to the city and in particular to its Roma inhabitants. The correction was applied for the entire census in a heavily politicised context.

and how they achieve their place and meaning in a political discourse and less about them as physical places. Naming is part of a continuous negotiation that allows a particular actor to interact with a partner of discussion and less an analytical term, let alone a technical one that the administration would use to classify an area, the practice of using the term ghetto in particular shows that this may be sometimes more or less of what that place really is.

The very fact that in Romanian these places are rarely called ghettos and that there is no other specific term for this particular form of rundown areas might be an indication of: a) the fact that authorities do not perceived them as a category but just as particular places, as accidental insertions in a normal urban tissue and b) that there is a policy of making their character invisible through a policy of ironic labelling (Dallas, The Merry Neighbourhood, NATO, Columbia, etc.) or of giving them a *no go area* status by stressing the dangers and difficulties that are associated with Roma communities perceived as homogenous groups that are ruling over a territory where different rules apply. The uncertainty of terminology and the complexity and ambiguity of the processes that take place in such areas are illustrated in the literature by the ghetto-banlieu debate (Wacquant, 2008) the absence of the State (Bourdieu, 1993), the segregation as a general mechanism to “deviate” a particular group (Maurin, 2004), the slum perspective: being it global (Davis, 2006) third-world (Lloyd, 1979) or a self-build defence as a right to be into the world (Turner, 1972). Regardless if we put the emphasis on squatting and the struggle to come out of the shadow (Newirth, 2006) or on general informality, as structural part of the formal (Laguerre, 1994) we have valid theoretical perspectives that can identify many of the elements that can be found in our particular examples. However, when it comes to frame the very complex and fluid reality of the small size Roma neighbourhoods in the Romanian urban context we might find out that the combination of ambiguous policies, internal dynamics and the sheer size of the places provides too little matter and of too diverse nature to allow the use of major theoretical instruments. At a glance, Doi Moldoveni is a *banlieu* that has a ghetto inside it, Livadă was born as a squatter settlement but has little to do with the mechanisms that established Kibera or Dharavi and Obor is a slum born out of a relocation of another slum in a manner that can be considered a slum upgrading programme but with strong elements of a ghetto. The choice to use mainly the term *urban ghetto* in this study is based on an attempt to highlight a phenomenon of spatial exclusion largely based on ethnicity and that is the result of local policies, but within a context of general racist attitudes, aiming to confine *the Roma* and *the poor* and especially *the poor Roma* on certain territories.

The various neighbourhoods of the city appear to have a strong identity in the view of the people we talked to, the borders are clearly defined and the name of the area is used as a marker of personal identity. There is also fear to cross some territories though the antagonism is mostly virtual and not associated with major violent episodes:

“Now it is ok, because it’s daytime, but if you come in the evening and see what’s in here you’ll get really scared! I’m afraid to go into the neighbourhood during the night!”

Fig. 3. „Doi Moldoveni” (Two Moldavians) as seen from the railway and over the abandoned land that separates it from the Spoitori neighbourhood, FNC-Livada.

Source: Author’s photo.

There are several areas that could be technically labelled as “disadvantaged housing areas”, some of them inhabited exclusively by Roma while some others, though predominantly Roma are to some extent mixed. The process of spatialization and racialization of poverty can be traced through individual stories but it is also present in the narratives and in the official papers of the City Hall. The areas are mostly located on the edges, fact of symbolic importance here as the size of the city makes the physical distances less relevant for segregation but they are defined by poor access and surrounded by impermeable or unfriendly limits. However, we should take into account that due to the overwhelming presence of industry and because of the peculiar development of the city alongside two main parallel roads that connect a city and two villages surrounded by industry this is the case for many other neighbourhoods. The poor and the Roma are, in principle, distinct categories that are strongly overlapping in all the locations we visited, the areas being trapped in between a central spine of a small city and a fading industrial belt.

Five Călărași, N6 aka “The Phantom”- approximately twenty families live here, in a block disconnected from sewage and all other utilities and that is proposed for demolition. “The worst places in town are Doi Moldoveni and Cinci Călărași, there you can find gangs of pimps that are strongly related to Spain, it’s better not to speak with anybody from there.” (male informant from Oborul Nou, around 40 years). Actually many people work with legal forms, some of them for the City.

Fig. 4. Five Călărași, N6 aka “The Phantom”.

Source: Author’s photo.

In addition to the difficult access the areas have uncertain legal status, are under-equipped in terms of utilities and infrastructure and have substandard housing. In order to have a general view of poverty housing in Călărași we listed all the seven areas in which the team conducted research but will describe just three of them in order to illustrate different typologies.

The poverty areas in which the Sparex research was conducted are the following: Oborul Nou, Cărămidari, FNC – Livadă, Doi Moldoveni, Cinci (Five) Călărași, Măgureni (Cireșoia, Muncei, Ostrovului), Prelungirea București (Fundătura Cazărmii).

Oborul Nou, Doi Moldoveni and Cinci Călărași are undoubtedly ghettos, respectively zones surrounded by strong symbolic and physical boundaries that are inhabited by communities that were formed through a process of social and economic exclusion that has deep roots in the current anti-gypsy attitudes. Whilst the first one is a recent urban development of individual houses the later are „classic” urban ghettos that follow a common pattern that can be found in the postcommunist city – former workers’ dormitories, *ab initio* precarious, now degraded and abandoned or administered in a strictly reactive manner using strategies that vary from brutal evictions followed by radical refurbishments and change of population to brutal restrictions of access to utilities followed by educational programmes run by NGOs, with EU money and in partnership with the same local administration that was the most active actor of the initial exclusion.

Fig. 5. Călărași, City map - Roma housing areas – with the exception of Five Călărași, placed near the main boulevard behind an important monument, all the other areas are peripheral.

FNC-Livadă is a territory that was taken into possession by a group of *Spoitori*, a compact community of blood related people with a long history of autonomy, an ethnical enclave in which aggregation and segregation are equally important. In Măgureni, Prelungirea București and Căramidari we can observe a traditional form of *mahala*, more ethnically mixed, with living conditions that are modest but mainly decent and in which you can find people that are exposed to different forms of housing vulnerability.

Oborul Nou

The area takes its name from the animal fair (Obor) and it is the result of a systematisation process that aimed to transform a former dumping area for construction debris into a housing area for a dislocated community of Turkish Roma. It was established in 2001 as an *urban development*, i.e. a type of urbanistic operation that is in perfect accord with the dominant ideology of the Romanian political class which, despite any right-left divide is in essence neoliberal. Urban development is naturally seen as *sprawl*, as new residential areas that would group families with a similar economic status that are largely autonomous in residential terms, able to manage their houses in every aspect and happy to live an individual life. The functional division of the modernist planners that consisted of working areas, leisure areas, residential areas etc. is still conserved as a manner of planning the city but aims to blast the socialist collective buildings by replacing them with an American suburb.

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Fig. 6. Oborul Nou – The green area is the former location of the community, they have been removed from there since the Street Prelungirea Slobozia became the main access road to the city as a connection to the highway.

Fig. 7. Oborul Nou. Typical view after rain.

Source: Author's photo.

Oborul Nou is placed in a marginal position beyond the peripheral road (str. Rocadei), separated by a heavy traffic road by the Sf. Lazăr cemetery and by an empty field that is crossed by the so called street Prelungirea I.L. Caragiale, a dirt road of about 300 m that is bordered by debris, illegally dumped in the area. There is another access road on the opposite side, passing by several small industrial facilities and connecting the community with a boulevard that ends in the nearby farm and that separates them from a small housing area with modest houses. The third access is a very long and very narrow pedestrian passage measuring about 200 meters in between the animal fair and a deposit, never used by women and children after sunset. All the properties that have a common boundary

with the area have tall, opaque, concrete or iron sheets fences, some topped with barbed wire. The opposite side is an empty plot of agricultural land, Bucovinei Street that can be found on the map is does not exist while Jiului is a dirt road boarded by three houses. The usual access is defined by a series of spatial events that follows the sequence: abandoned silo, cemetery, truck road, dirt road boarded by debris, Oborul Nou, nothing (city border).

This „Turkish” neighbourhood is a municipal initiative to allocate plots of land to poor families that were living in Căramidari in a place that was *beautified* and replaced by a park. The relocation of the community is in relative spatial and historical continuity with the *mahala* of Căramidari, the area of the park being used by the inhabitants as a clay pit, the name, which in Romanian means „brick producers” being a clear indication of the local trade of the people. According to local accounts produced by the *Spoitori* the place was filthy and dangerous, full of miserable shacks, mud and garbage, populated with angry people whom nobody wanted to deal with. The perspective of the former inhabitants is much calm, extreme poverty, no electricity and hard work. The houses were demolished; the land was levelled and turned into a park. Most of the people were given plots of land on a piece of land behind the graveyard that was established at the same time with the Roma neighbourhood. Later on, the graveyard was further extended towards the houses, using a last piece of empty land.

Fig. 8. Oborul Nou and its neighbouring areas

Source: Google Maps.

The 110 plots are relatively large, measuring in between 300 and 350 square meters and are granted for 49 years, the annual fee being from 400 to 500 Euro. Around seven families are sued every year in order to recuperate old debts, some of them never paid and the amount of debt for ten years is now overwhelming for many inhabitants. The situation is similar in Livada where there is an even larger amount of debt. The apparently generous idea of granting young families a piece of land on which they would be able, using their own means, to build a house, is here severely constrained by the limit imposed by the subsistence economy, by the general lack of education, actually by the high level of illiteracy and functional illiteracy and of the high level of exclusion from the labour market which affect even the few qualified Roma.

The piece of land selected for the new neighbourhood was previously occupied in part by an orchard, the rest being used as a dumping area for construction debris. Some inhabitants accuse the softness of the soil, claiming it is unstable for constructions and there are many places where you have landfill, however it is hard to be recorded as fact in the absence of a geological survey and taking into consideration the very poor structural quality of the houses, particularly that of the foundations that actually creates the instability. The orthogonal grid is simple, with plots and streets properly sized and shaped, with sidewalks but without pavement or drainage system. There is little infrastructure besides electricity, water is provided by three pumps but recent works almost completed a water supply system that goes around the margins of the community and might provide in the future individual access to water. For the moment there are only a handful of houses that have individual water supply. There is no gas or sewage, nor public transportation in the vicinity.

Locating a residential area behind a graveyard and an animal fair is a planning gesture that indicates an urban policy oriented towards active exclusion. It is nevertheless a common urban policy in terms of housing: individual housing in private property has a highly valued symbolical value that opposes the communal buildings, the blocks of flats with social houses that are seen by many as an absolute evil, as an error of the former regime. The stigma that is associated in post communist Romania with living in common premises and the overrating of individual housing led to an uncontrolled expansion of the suburbs, an urban sprawl ideologically coloured as “development” and that was produced by the most dynamic members of the society. The imposition of the same model on poverty communities is not a logical fallacy but a cover-up for the creation of ghettos. There is little difference, both in urban planning terms and in the political discourse between that particular form of slum relocation, that transforms it into a real ghetto, and the *Villagio dela Solidarita* from Rome, where informal camps from the inner city were relocated 30 km away from the centre in order to insure better housing conditions or the French *village d’insertion*, a modern form of prison for some of the Roma in Aubervilliers. This form of ghetto is a well concealed form of institutional racism that can be seen as a failure of a modernisation process that was done in good

will by the authorities but lacked the full support of the inhabitants. The tangent position is here by no means the expression of a development that could not take place in a too dense urban centre but of an intentional choice to hide the unwanted population behind a set of different barriers.

That has to do with the identity of these people, as Ali, their leader says: „We are Turkish, not Horahane or Gypsies, I mean... our elders came from Bulgaria so we are Bulgarian Turkish Roma!” The inhabitants of Obor have different origins and some use different identities. It is fair to assume that out of the approximately 600 inhabitants of Obor just the 412 self declared Turks are indeed Turks and the others have different origins; some Spoitori, some Cărămidari, some Horahane from Medgidia and Babadag and several Romanians. For all the areas, except Livadă, we can observe that mixture is significant and can end up being the main rule, like in Măgureni where most families are mixed. The order of identities in the self-description and the number of ethnonyms used is relevant for the dynamics of identity, actually a formula that traces back the history, the culture, the race and the current social position.

Ali is somehow in between a leader and a mediator in Obor, not really qualified or interested in performing any of the functions but able to give to the Mayor some grip, presumably electoral, on the community. He is now employed by the City as a cemetery administrator, position that makes his neighbours refer to him as „The Mayor”. He is Turkish, he has a brother in law in Istanbul where he worked for several years and where one of his sons is born. During the last elections he supported the contender, not in an open way but for sure in an effective one for now he has a position in the City. „When the Mayor needs us, he just calls, we go there and he tells us what to do.” This is the job description of what he does, he never complains about his neighbourhood, he actually managed to buy a larger piece of land across the street, not far from the land he received from the City and which he sold it to another Turkish family. Though he lives just 200 meters away from his former place and has access from the same street as all the other inhabitants people say he doesn't live in Obor anymore but in the „Romanian part”.

External accounts of identity are also meaningful for the definition of the very low position of the Turks on local level. When asked if amongst the Spoitori there are people that are as poor as the Turks, their leader, Meraru answered:

The Turks?! Have you been there? They are better now then how it was, in the place that is now a park there were some frightening pits and wild vegetation. You were afraid to go there by night because someone, of course some of them, would hit on you. These Turks are *Țigani*... that sort of *șogori*⁵. We don't get into

⁵ *Sogor* is a Hungarian term that means brother-in-law and has an ironical conotation in the south, mocking up the way Hungarians speak. Here it is used totally unrelated to the Turks but in order to outline the major difference between them and the Spoitori.

their way, they don't get into ours. Because our kin is the most gentle in Walachia, they are well behaved and fearsome. The Spoitori are slow [i.e. measured], fearless and humane. I can see how the Turks live because I have a house of one nephew of mine there, he's away and we rented to two individuals and now they are ten, because they don't have where to live. You can stay there if you wish, just sleep one on top of the other! (Leader from the Spoitor community, Călărași, May 2012).

Fig. 9. Oborul Nou after the rain.

Source: Author's photo.

The lack of water creates a serious vulnerability to fire; one of the houses situated in the immediate vicinity of the community centre was rebuilt with some help from the City (emergency funds) after a fire that claimed the life of three children, aged in between seven months and four years, left alone by their mother. The case was presented with lots of details by the media and one inhabitant declared: „Nobody cares about us; the nearest water supply is one kilometre away. Our Mayor only invests in churches and parks; he only needs us when elections come!” Another case happened in 2007, for which we couldn't find reports, but according to Terrance, the leader of the community centre, a four years old boy died while his sister escaped through the window. They lost the house and they tried to buy a new one, the cheapest that could be found being at that time in Doi Moldoveni, a single room apartment with no bathroom in a four stories high prefabricated block of flats at a cost of around 5000\$. When asking for a house he found out that many of the actual inhabitants of Obor don't have legal papers and that some of them have received eviction orders. This is an indication, and not the only one, that further research might show that there is a significant part of dwellers that are actually renting or sub-letting the houses.

According to Valentin, a former inhabitant of Doi Moldoveni who now lives in the community centre run by Terrance, some people in Obor arrived from the centre of the city as a result of the retrocession process:

It's not like you mention about Cluj (I told him about the forced evictions in Coastei case), they were not sent to the garbage pit but here, near the cemetery, just to remind them where we all have to end up. I see here some racism, a way to put together people of same ethnicity in an enclosure. That fence that you saw was even bigger, they cut that alley that is so scary that children, and almost nobody uses it and the Cemetery was smaller and now it is extended to the margins of the neighbourhood. On the other entrance all sort of people and businesses are throwing their garbage. One day I saw children with syringes of veterinary use in their hands, I made a complaint to the Police, I also took photos, but nobody answered. The dogs are also a big problem, especially in the morning, previously I was picking up children from home but now, after so many attacks, I prefer to give a call to their parents. If I would change something in this neighbourhood, and I wouldn't speak about mentality, I would take the dogs and the garbage away and put at least some stone on the roads. (Valentin, male, 37 years old, former inhabitant from Doi Moldoveni now living in Obor Nou, interviewed in May 2012, Călărași).

Fig. 10. Oborul Nou after the rain: a typical dwelling with closed veranda.
Source: Author's photo.

The dwellings of Oborul Nou are quite typical for the entire south of Romania, most of the poverty houses being developed under a very simple scheme; a single room unit, usually almost square and of a length that varies in

between three to four meters receives a second room, with a separate entrance and a small veranda, first opened, then closed and used as a kitchen. The veranda faces the South and its major role is to protect the entrance against the extreme continental climate with very hot summers and very cold winters. This particular house is a work in progress of a very young family with two kids, and it is a typical overlapping of layers of works that are executed after every return of the husband from Italy. Most of the houses in Obor use just several stones as a foundation and the walls are made of adobe bricks. The work is done by paid workers; it is rarely the case when a family has the skills and physical strength to execute a house for them. Despite the fact that the informal market of construction works is extremely cheap, it still does not work very well, at least in terms of regularity. Actually, what I noticed during the years was that there were sudden, major outbursts of constructions which contrasted to long periods of very low activity and chronic lack of maintenance. There is no steady progress; just random periods of furious investment for the family that manages to get some money.

Fig. 11. Inside the homes from Oborul Nou.

Source: Author's photo.

The room is tidy, the flooring (the cheapest laminated parquet) lies directly on the ground, the inventory is modest, an expandable couch, a small table, a stove and a mirror. The veranda/kitchen hosts a recycled cupboard filled with several objects about which the woman says: "if you leave the door opened, somebody would steal even these".

Fig. 12. Yard and veranda in Oborul Nou

Source: Author's photo.

The entrance alley is done with broken pieces from the prefabricated concrete fence of the graveyard. The roof is covered with metal sheets that lay on a thin, rare structure made of the cheapest wood available, the very gentle slope of the side that covers the hall posing serious threats in case of heavy snow.

Fig. 13. Inside a house in construction from Oborul Nou.

Source: Author's photo.

„I would like to have some parquet in here, if God helps!”, said the owner of the house in construction pictured in Fig. 13. It is often the case that the second room is unfinished, even when done it is rarely used otherwise than a deposit for the stuff they might have. In rural Romania it is called “the good room” or “the big room”. However, considering the fact that heating and maintaining a second room is not affordable we can hardly attribute the important number of unfinished room to tradition. Actually, the percentage of unused/unfinished rooms might be a very good indicator of housing deprivation in a poverty area.

Fig. 13. The designed interior of a home in Oborul Nou.

Source: Author’s photo.

This particular family was interesting to follow for its dynamics, a more recent visit showing an impressive advance in finishing and furniture on the basis of some money that came from Italy; she managed to get her parquet and nice blue walls but there was no stove inside, nor money to get one before winter. However, this achievement came with a price, her twenty one years old husband had his brachial artery and nerve sectioned, a major injury with possible permanent mobility and sensitivity effects, in an event that was not revealed, she just present it as “heart problems”. Considering that the extended family was involved in a violent attack with “swords” (long makeshift knives, a machete type that is very popular in places affected by insecurity) and that his work in recycling does not require sharp tools it is likely that this was the result of a violent episode.

It is hard to know to what extent the remittances have a positive impact on the living conditions for the majority of the families involved in the process of circular migration and how many people really take advantage of their work, our survey did not get much evidence for successful migrants in Oborul Nou, most of the success stories being located in the Spoitori neighbourhood, FNC-Livadă.

FNC-Livadă

There is a certain preference of the people of Călărăși to use acronyms and names that contain numerals (Doi Moldoveni = Two Moldavians; Cinci Călărăși = Five Călărăși; Zece Niveluri = Ten Stories etc.); in this case FNC means “Fabrica de nutrețuri combinate” (Combined Forage Factory), an industrial objective that is a major landmark in the Northern brownfields while “Livadă” means orchard, which was the former use of a part of the land on which the Spoitori settled starting with the la 90’s. It is to be supposed that this sort of toponymy is a marker of the rapid development on a flat territory that lacks major historical, cultural or geographical references. This sort of strategy still keeps the flavour of the pioneering groups, heterogeneous groups of colonists that were rapidly settling on a cultureless territory in a military manner and with no interests to bring an ethos other then the one of efficiency and production.

Fig. 14. Livada, Călărăși.

Source: Google Maps.

Due to the different cultural status of the *Spoitori* group, their attempt to constitute a settlement *ex-nihilo* follows a different political path, in an attempt of the authorities to create a site-specific area several streets are named after famous Roma personalities: the actor Ștefan Bănică, the violin player Ion Voicu etc. Livadă is a bottom-up initiative, a case in which a community with a strong identity, a particular dynamic and a long history in the area is appropriating a territory in order to defend its livelihoods and lifestyle.

Fig. 15. Livada, two of the industrial limits of the neighbourhood towards FNC, one towards Doi Cocoși, the other that ends with a small empty area and a motel.

Source: Author's photo.

Livada and Doi Moldoveni are separated by the railway, the ruins of a former industrial area and a graveyard. The place is full of debris and aggressive stray dogs. Children and old people are under constant attack from the dogs but they don't care much, their ability to fight back keeps the balance. Livada stretches in between the truck road, the FNC, the Doi Cocoși neighbourhood (to the South, practically indistinguishable from Livada) and the railway.

The area has a peri-urban character, the gardens are too small to be productive and people don't have too many animals but the infrastructure, the public space and the public equipments are minimal or missing. Due to the particular process of formation the street network is unevenly developed and sized,

there are a number of dead ends that are not suited for auto access. Local shops are well supplied and the merchandise on the shelves is an illustration of an almost urban type of consumption, with little to no presence of fresh food – typical to periphery shops where this is supplied by local production, sometimes some more expensive alcohol, all sorts of detergents and personal care products. The way the products are arranged and the advertising show that the shops are connected to the main networks of distribution. However there is an important variation of the stock, sometimes just one of the two shops works and the diversity can disappear overnight and be replaced by the usual minimal list of products that are characteristic to a poverty area shop – bread, beer, oil, sugar, very cheap sweets, matches and maybe some canned meat products. Proximity shops in that sort of areas are an excellent instantaneous indicator of the economic level of a community, the Metaxa cogniac that was there during the wedding season is now replaced by a long list of debtors, all waiting for some money from Italy. Not everybody is “on the notebook”, the sums are small and the repayment time is short, sign of a relatively good economic situation of the community. In comparison, in Obor very few people can get food from the nearby shops on credit.

A brief history of the Spoitori

The community has a dramatic history of relocations that started in 1981, at the apex of Ceaușescu’s programme to build new civic centers for every county capital and to systematize rural areas. For twenty years the community was splitted in several villages around Călărași, finally they managed to reunite through a spectacular agregation process that involved buying properties, squatting and negotiating with authorities like a real political body. The interview with nea Costică “Meraru” (Tudorache Constantin), the leader of the Spoitori, brings not only the story of relocations but a wealth of other informations about the lifestyle and livelihoods of his group. He was born in 1935 in Mircea Vodă, at that time when the commune was not part of the city. According to an observation that I owe to the late Nicolae Gheorghe, Meraru is a live history book of the community, an oral register of the kinship relations having a fundamental functional role in regulating the weddings, the economy of respect and hierarchy or the cohesion in front of common threats. This is how what explains his position as a leader; he is obviously not the wealthiest or the strongest but the keeper of the collective memory. This was striking during the interview, many events, though happened more then 30-40 years ago, were mentioned with the exact date and most of the persons were mentioned with their full name. His narrative technique is not only well polished through practice but also built on innate qualities like the pleasure to share with you various stories but still keep to the topic, the care for details that is associated with a sort of balance and respect for persons and that is elegantly laid upon events that were probably not as dignifying as they look now. However, the construction of the discourse is almost invisible; his goal is to act as an objective source that represents historical events from a

mature perspective, the narrative has an ethical role, more like a captain's log than of a contemporary blog. This is not to say that the narrative has a technical or neutral style but that the usual overwhelming personal references that are common for non-professional communicators are not here. His discourse had the political function of a report; I was introduced to him by somebody from the City Hall and he also knew that I am from Bucharest so he imagined that he can deliver some messages. Meraru is a gentle gatekeeper that knows the general geography of power and is also able to connect it to the local, minor leadership or with the somehow active but still loose structures of the Roma Party (Partida Romilor):

Sometimes Nicu Paun (Roma MP) comes, we make a meeting, he asks us what we need, tells us what we have to do. He is almost more powerful than the Mayor!

(...)

[About the "communist times":] The world was fine then, the old ones were educated, how to say, less able to communicate. We had cattle, two, three, some even ten, my parents had twelve and were providing for the officer's kitchen here, at 23, 20 and 5 Călărași on a regular basis. Down the valley there was a grazing field as large as you could see with your eyes and the animals were separated in two herds, the ones that could give milk and the non-productive. We had a good life, the calves were on contract with the state, we had money. The houses were small, with two rooms, or two rooms and hall, the land was in between 250-300 sqm. The families were not too large, there were two to five children and, at that time there were no separate rooms for children, like they have now even as early as seven month old but until the child was two he was sleeping in the arms of his mother. After four or five he was given his own bed.

(...)

After a while, what happened; the wetland was cultivated with corn, with grains, that's the way Ceaușescu was, greedy, he wanted to cultivate all the land, anyhow, it was better than now. You were free at your home, with your money, you were safe! When the pasture disappeared we gave the animals to the state company. The community was not more different than today, about 400 families, now we are 600, I counted them, more than 3000 people because today people have lots of children, five, six, even seven, even the dumbest has at least three.

(...)

In 1981, the 21st of July, we were demolished and moved, some at Cuza Vodă, some at Ceacu, others at Roseți, some others at Tonea, we split. They needed our land which was in between Călărași and Mircea Vodă; we were in the middle and we were told that we are illegal. Some got some land from the cooperatives, the ones who got money bought houses in the village and then we spent 14 years there, in Roseți and Tonea. From Roseți we draw back to Tonea, you know we, the Roma, are like sheep, if one jumps into a well all the others will jump too! The Bulibașa was one of my uncles, Leca Constantin, he did not agree with the demolition, he tried to contact Ceaușescu, but the Mayor and other people from

the City finally did that and we had to move from here to there until we spotted this empty piece of land and we moved here in 1996. (Leader of the Spoitor community, Călărași, May 2012).

I also asked him to give details about the process of settlement and about their current legal status:

I have papers for the land, me and my neighbours, we bought it from somebody but the rest live on the municipal land under a concession contract, they don't pay for the house, it is considered a garden. This land belonged to Mr. Tărăcilă, he inherited it. When the City saw us on the land, with no papers, no permits, they made an exchange, they gave him 25 hectares in the agricultural area in exchange for his land here. We were very content because we were allowed to build houses, we particularly liked this mayor, Mr. Dragu, we voted for him twice because he made us this service. He said: 'Do what you have to do but don't take more than 250 sqm. If you have children and they are married it's a different family, so they will also get 250, so we put everybody in line and we distributed as it should, 500 for one, 1000 for another, the smallest was 150 because I told them, sometimes in the future we'll have to pay for it. We also let streets in between us, we need streets. People gathered here, in the centre, it took about a week but I would only need a single day if they would have been at home all at a time, it was simple because they listen to me, they love and respect me, I am their leader since 1973, the month of August, on the 16th and I was their leader in Roseți and Tonea as well. I have reached a certain age, people saw I take care of them, I never need a *bacșiș* (i.e. tip), and nobody can say he gave me even a bottle of beer. (Leader of the Spoitor community, Călărași, May 2012)

Fig. 16. House for sale in the Spoitor community from Călărași, the contact number written with paint on the wall is Italian.

Source: Author's photo.

„These are the children that left for work!” House for sale, the contact number written with paint on the wall is Italian. It is not the only one, several houses have their doors and windows blocked with panels or masonry, a clear indication of the fact that the inhabitants are away for a long period.

Călărași has a strong connection with Naples, so strong that people in Naples think that all Romanian Roma are from Călărași, local authorities claiming that there could be as much as 5000 people in the city and its suburbs. Meraru gives us one of the reasons for their massive migration:

Some others that left for Italy came back and demolished the old house that was smaller, modest and made a better one, with a nice fence, aligned with the street. The new houses are different from the old ones. When the evaluator from Bucharest came, Mr. Persican Dumitru, we agreed at a price, first it was 20 Euros, then 15 but we settled at 10 Euro/sqm, people pay the rent but some have already the contracts to buy it. Everybody wants to buy but if you have 200 sqm you have to pay 2000 Euros, many have to lend the money, in our community you have to pay interest, for 2000 in five to six month you have to pay 2-300 Euros more. People get along very well, they help one another, it is most likely that more than half of them will buy the land. Here, in the city there is no work, maybe from our kin, the Spoitori, of which we might be 1200 families, only about forty have a job, but only stinky jobs: night-guard, street sweeper, longshoreman, garbage man at the pit. But we used to have a good life with the cattle! (Leader of the Spoitor community, Călărași, May 2012).

The relation with the City is not always smooth; there are problems that arise from the lack of legal status and sometimes from the many weddings that are taking place in the public space.

There was a water pipe here, on the main street, when the Romanians had their gardens, when they left the pumps remain, now we are promised that we will also have water and the roads are good, when we came here there was mud all over the place, we are content with him (the Mayor) because he provided... Before him there was another one, who did what he did: there were three very poor men, two brothers in law and a brother and they made some shacks that were so small and poor that you were ashamed to go in and Mr Mayor Mițan came with a bulldozer and knocked them down. He said: you are not allowed to build, you don't have permits. Then Mr Dragu came and said: Do what you can, but I don't want to hear any noise, no conflict, nothing in Tribunal or at the Prefect, I don't want to have troubles. Make your houses as you like it but keep them in line, the street should look nice and we'll see what we do further! People got that and everybody respected the rules. The largest house here has six rooms for like six individuals. The smallest, the houses of the poor have two rooms and a hall. The biggest problem here is the

lack of sewage. Until now it was not even possible because of the railway but now there is sewage on the nearby boulevard and we hope to be connected. (Leader of the Spoitor community, Călărași, May 2012).

Fig. 17. Livada – normal density of housing, small courtyards with some chicken and few fancy rooftops that were quickly labelled as “palaces” by the visitors.
All houses are only ground level.

Source: Author’s photo.

Doi Moldoveni

Migration during socialist times was important but after the 1977 earthquake and during the vast construction programmes of the 80’s it reached unprecedented levels. An important part of it was based in Moldova (the Romanian historical region, not the actual Republic of Moldova) and alongside with it came the stigma associated with the Moldavians as poor, uneducated, violent, noisy etc. Nobody really knows why the neighbourhood is named Doi Moldoveni (Two Moldavians) but it is for sure that many Moldavians came to live here when Siderca, the metallurgic company was under construction. The symbolic hierarchies place the Moldavians at the bottom and the ideas that are associated with the populations of recent migrants were close to racist stereotypes in those years (more fertile than average, promiscuous, dirty, barbarians that destroyed the local culture etc.)

Fig. 19. Doi Moldoveni, Călărași.

Source: Google Maps.

The name „Doi Moldoveni” is nothing else but the fixation of this relation between the locals and the migrant other, in this case in the form of an ironic mythology of two Moldavians about whom nobody can tell if they were friends or foes but about which pretty much everybody thinks it has to do with a pub. This is no different from the most important ghetto of today in Romania, Aleea Livezilor in Ferentari, Bucharest where the informal name used by some policeman was TMT (țărani, moldoveni, țigani) – PMG (peasants, Moldavians, Gypsies), a formula that describes with sociological accuracy both the social and ethnical composition and the local hierarchy (Berescu, 2011).

We are accustomed with the idea of a ghetto that has strong and visible physical boundaries however, though some of the limits of urban ghettos are easy identifiable some others are more loose and permeable. For the block of flats typology there is rarely the case when there is a ghetto surrounded by an average standard neighbourhood; always the ghetto is a part of a larger poverty area with which it trades its symbolic boundaries. An exterior perspective, of an occasional visitor of a an inhabitant of a distant area of the city is usually taking into account an extended area and collects fears and stereotypes (e.g. Ferentari in Bucharest or Brixton in London as problematic neighbourhoods). Coming closer to it there is a larger poverty area with substandard but functional houses and where access is non problematic. Then there is a ghetto that defines its limits in accordance to where your informant lives; for some their own place is the worst, for others is always the neighbour who is the You know you are in a ghetto when people start to ask you: What are you doing here?

Fig. 19. Doi Moldoveni. Block of flats in a very bad shape, families still dwelling there.
Source: Author's photo.

The neighbourhood is situated at the end of a larger zone of blocks of flats that is mainly composed of four stories buildings made of prefabricated concrete panels, typical urban planning of the 70's on following the principles of the Athena Chart, a totally non-site specific approach that is disconnected from the neighbouring urban tissue. A common unintentional irony that can be found in many other ghettos makes it start where the street Belșugului (The Wealth Street) ends⁶. All the units that are affected by poverty have a similar structure: one staircase with single room apartments most likely a typified project of IPCT Bucharest (The Institute for Typified Constructions).

Besides interviews with the inhabitants of Doi Moldoveni we had the chance to meet Valentin B, 37 years, a former inhabitant of Doi Moldoveni, now recruited by a team of Christian missionaries to work and live in the community centre in Oborul Nou. His story is important because he lived from the late 80's in various places in Doi Moldoveni then he left in 2012 from an apartment that he still owns; now he lives in the centre with his wife. His personal trajectory is in a way particular, for he is raised in an orphanage, but then again his relation to the

⁶ Some other examples are: The Springtime Street in Miercurea Ciuc, by the sewage plant, Nadejda (Hope), one of the largest ghettos in Europe in Sliven, Bulgaria, The Landscape Street in Bucharest or Fakulteta in Sofia.

place is illustrative for the process that changed the area. During communism he graduated high school and was employed in the steel works factory. Alongside with that he received a room in Doi Moldoveni but only after few month, in the aftermath of the Revolution, he lost his job and was thrown out – „last to come, first to go!”. For about one year he had to sleep in various places, he rent, he slept rough in the railway station or in the park, until one day when he decided to ask for a meeting with the director of the company. He was employed again and got a room that he eventually bought after the privatisation. The house was bought with the money he received as compensation – six monthly salaries, around 240 million lei in 1998, out of which the price of the house was 200 millions, roughly 4500 E. Today the cheapest price for a piece is 2,200 Euro for a legal purchase but to occupy a room that is free it only costs 20 million (2,000 lei – 450 Euro).

My struggle was to get a room in the block by the military headquarters that was the cleanest, there was a very good administrator there, a Hungarian woman, Venera, very tough woman, maybe a little racist because she was not taking gipsies in the block. It might be that I could not get there, I am dark haired, dark skinned (Valentin, male, 37 years old, a former inhabitant of Doi Moldoveni, now living in Obor Nou, interviewed in May 2012).

Valentin witnessed the dynamics of change of this worker's dormitories neighbourhood whose inhabitants were predominantly young males, some living three to four in a 19sqm room that had a sink and a small hall used as a kitchen, with common toilets on the corridor. Using the existing sewage some of them equipped their rooms with private toilets and showers.

I see an enormous difference since 1993, when I first received a room, at that time there were a lot of Moldavians, of course, and very few Roma. There were problems with the Moldavians at that time, they were getting drunk and then... At that time life was not that bad, the place was green, and there was tranquillity. Starting with '95 the Moldavians started to leave and the plant closed. During the closing procedures there was a guy who was distributing rooms and I witnessed how many Spoitori started to sell their apartment in the city and move in here. This way they could have some money but still own a house. (Valentin, male, 37 years old, a former inhabitant of Doi Moldoveni, now living in Obor Nou, interviewed in May 2012).

Near the military headquarters one of the blocks, previously used for high school students, was refurbished and the former inhabitants removed. One of the rooms at the ground level hosts a local police office.

Since various people came I feel insecure. They only care about the interiors of their house but the exterior space is a disaster. The Spoitori have very nice houses on the inside but several years ago I was afraid to look on the window, such a general mess there was, a lot more dirty than today. We had to close the common bathroom; everybody made his own toilet and

shower. There were lots of rats, bugs, mosquitoes, dogs, once I saved a woman from a violent attack of a pack of dogs. I would never live in Doi Moldoveni and raise a child there but I could live here in Obor among these people, I would make myself a house out of containers and I would be fine, here is less dangerous. I thought about it a lot, there I am an owner, I have furniture, the house might worth 300 million lei (6,700 Euro), it has a shower and air conditioning but I would never go back. I saw families that moved there because there was no other choice and in several month their children, that were first very respectful where 'touched' by the zone. Prostitution is flourishing, even the wife of the pimp who attacked me came to me to offer a girl, and that was during the day! Prostitution is not only local, the main activity takes place at Podul 4 (Bridge 4), even in Obor sometimes you can find during the night expensive cars, you wonder what they do here and you see girls that maybe, don't came at age that are dressed in a very provocative way. But here, in Obor, things are not so visible; in Doi Moldoveni even the persons who should do their duty... I don't want to tell, I am scared of the thought that I might live there again! (Valentin, male, 37 years old, a former inhabitant of Doi Moldoveni, now living in Obor Nou, interviewed in May 2012).

Vasile I., the leader in Doi Moldoveni, a former leader of the Roma Party that now leads an NGO, comes from a Spoitori family with eleven brothers. Kinship explains as much of his local power as his native intelligence and diligent attitude: he is an author of a book that he hopes to publish soon and his interests and knowledge about Roma issues is way above average. He is a polemic individual, the common blaming of the leaders being pushed by him up at a higher level, as he accuses the central leaders and the main figures of Roma activism for the general bad situation of today. Though he is a very good speaker, he is not too much liked by municipality officials. His leadership has more to do with the administration of the block of flats. Actually, like in any neighbourhood of blocks of flats, there is no community of interest beyond the staircase.

Policy Discussion and Conclusions

Urban policies

The urban and spatial policy of the municipality is in line with the practice in most of the Romanian cities but it can be argued that it is actually being one of the softest positions towards Roma. The process of segregation – aggregation is not driven through active policies but is based on past events and follows inherited trends. Segregation comes in steps; it is built on innate vulnerabilities and covered by a discourse about development. Two of the actual neighbourhoods, Doi Moldoveni and Livadă are a result of both communist policies and neoliberal transition trends. During communism, it was argued through the voice of

Ceașescu himself that the collective housing estates were the best way to spare more land for agriculture, in fact that was the way to concentrate the workforce needed for the megalomaniac industrial programmes. We witness today an opposite turn, as well ideologically driven and idealized through a discourse that values the suburban house as the „normal” way of living and as the cradle of the anticommunist middle class, the real driving force (or in a conspiracy theory terminology „the agent with a hidden agenda”) being in that case the real estate market, precisely that part that speculates on land and houses in order to take advantage of the „property bubbles”. The disintegration of public spaces has to do with the strong flow of inhabitants towards periphery, a major source of environmental damage for most cities. This post-revolutionary middle class dream is not what drives the Roma communities towards the edge of the city but the values on which it is built are in use when it comes to relocation plans.

The development of new residential areas for young families’ works actually in the case of Obor as a process of spatial exclusion of the poor, even when some of the initial conditions were properly established; in this case, decent size individual plots placed on a correct grid of streets. The failure to achieve the relative success of the new residential areas composed of individual housing is not just a temporary stage of a development process that is just lagging behind but a permanent condition of a group excluded on ethnic and economic basis. Like in many other cases, the improvement of infrastructure or any other real advance in the living conditions, less likely to happen on the edge of the city, will only lead to a change of population like in any other gentrification process.

In order to give an answer to the failures of individual housing but to further keep it alive and valid as a model in the long run, authorities and civil society are employing the very popular strategy of building community centres, institutions that are primarily dedicated to children and have the main goal to discipline them and teach them hygiene. The focus on children, hugely popular amongst NGO’s, morally comfortable and practically less challenging than any other type of intervention is a disguise for a general, old style soteriology of saving the poor by educating their children, institutes a noble report between the benefactor and the *beneficiary* (*sic!*, this is the current terminology for any person that receives any sort of attention from an institution) but hides the permanent and enduring exclusion of their parents. Oborul Nou has two of them, one based on a Christian missionary mission and the second build with European funding and now administered by the municipality. This highlights the ghetto character of the neighbourhood no less stronger in a place like Doi Moldoveni, where you have ethnical mixture but less poignant in Livadă, a case that is at the end of the scale of segregation which is beautifully balanced with a very strong process of aggregation.

Identity as a segregation tool

The question of identity in regards with the build environment is always central in shaping attitudes and behaviours, ultimately urban policies, and points to a certain type of well established vision on Roma, essentialist in nature. The power practices it on the assumption that the lifestyle and the housing needs of Roma are different from the majority. This way they can capitalise on the general racist attitude and use it as a political argument when it comes to improving or maintaining housing conditions and the infrastructure. There is a strong political logic that draws from the fact that the majority is racist so the policy measures would not contradict this and eventually stabilize it in more or less subtle forms of institutional racism. Despite their apparently good intentions Roma support programmes are often shaped in this manner; traditional trades, traditional way of life, preserving the customs etc. Moreover, there is an activists' national project (Matei, 2012) that envisages the emancipation of Roma through reconquering their identity and unifying the past, easy to use by any form of power to treat disadvantaged groups as a radical alterity apparition that can be subjected to a different treatment than the majority. In addition, from the academic world, we have a long established line of Romani studies that tend to focus their investigations on the central question: What is a Roma? and to bring into the discussion a lot of knowledge about the differences between the Roma and the Gadje. As far as this may illustrate very well issues related to various everyday life and general activities that are generally labelled with the term *culture* it is less relevant in terms of architecture and even settlements structure – the classic terms urbanism or urban planning would be misleading in this context – and this is especially valid for the Romani ghettos. The inference is the following: the more poor the dwellers are, the less ethnic identity you can find in their build environment. It's only the rich Roma that can afford to invent/construct/perform identity and it is predominantly poverty, not ethnicity that shapes the physical aspect of the ghettos. It is very hard to find issues related to space use in housing, or urban setting (public space, common space) or any other spatial aspect (landscape, territorial usage, courtyards) that would be specific to Roma and not the others, especially in a settled (i.e. non-nomad) culture like that of the Romanian Roma. Even the very popular "Gypsy towers", of which one can find some miniatural versions in Livada, "towers" that are so popular among photographers are not exactly a Roma creation but a part of a vernacular culture in which the Romanian neighbours play a major part. Vividly coloured houses can also be spotted in Livadă but this is not common only for Livada and, despite the stereotype of colourful Roma houses can be attributed by large to an increased availability of colour paint – a major DIY shop that covers the entire county was built and with a sudden drop of the price in the late 2000's.

Ghetto Governance

The main policy issues that are related to the administration of these areas, and the reinforcement of their ghetto character, are related to the the lack of civil society and the feudal character of local leadership. The *state of exception* character of the policies that have to do with Roma and the the *emergency help* policy are adding to the *no go area* status that is ruled by strong leaders and can only be administered through middlemen. Călărași is a small city with virtually no active civil society (i.e. NGO, independent media, non-partisan critics, public intellectuals etc.). This has to do with the much accused communist heritage, or even with a longer line of historical determinants as nowadays Romanian intellectuals like to point out and with the general framework of decentralisation that shapes the behaviour of the administration. Due to the limits of our study it is not our goal to challenge the concept of „cultural heritage of communism” or to find out if the media term „local barons” is illustrative for the Mayor or the local Prefect. Nonetheless, our discussions with the inhabitants revealed several issues. First, the inhabitants’ perspective on power is massively dominated by the figure of the Mayor. When the Mayor doesn’t deliver they take into consideration „going to Bucharest”, never quite clear where to but to some superior forum. Otherwise he has it all: everything that has to do with decisions, from the big issues to the individual access to social canteen („He didn’t even give me the canteen!”). Thus he is able to capitalise on every current activity of his administrative apparatus. Second, the experience with power is limited to the interaction with few middlemen (mediators, Roma experts, juridical personnel). Many of the poor Roma are illiterate or functionally illiterate so they have to rely on their leaders and on the mediators, sometimes named, ironically, „our Mayor”. All these are regarded to a large extent as leaders and held accountable correspondingly. Third, the internal leadership of the communities is restrained to very few functions; it is vague and not always soft. Leadership has its benefits, largely exaggerated by the poor, always ready to present their leaders in the back as profiteers, slick and ruthless exploiters of the unfortunate, mainly the ones that got rich by keeping for themselves most of the things that were supposed to be distributed to the members of the community.

Roma leaders in poor communities are always secondary figures; they either lack real power or do not have minimal skills to act as political actors, or both. Their role is decorative for the administration, they are occasionally invited to round tables or used as a “portavoce” (i.e. voice amplifier) by the Mayor. There is no leadership in Cinci Călărași, Măgureni or Prelungirea București, but some forms in the other areas. For Livadă, *Bulibașul* Meraru is a classic figure of a patriarch with soft leadership skills that were acquired through practice, although his position is inherited through kinship. His power comes from the unity of the *neam* (kin) of Spoitori, whose behaviour is predictable.

The messages he has to deliver to the community are simple instructions to keep the order and how to vote, whilst the messages he is delivering from the community to the administration are simple and reasonable requests for improving the living conditions of his community. The individual requests are dealt by the mediators like for example DS, local Roma expert that has a relatively short history of dealing with Roma issues. According to his own story, he rarely used his Roma identity before 1989; he was fully integrated in the Romanian society, having a Romanian wife and working as a taxi driver until relatively recently. His organizing skills and polite behaviour made him the leader of the local branch of the Roma Party (Partida Romilor). It is a relatively important position since the MP cabinet of the Roma Deputy is situated in Călărași. However, not speaking the Romani language and not being part of a compact community puts him into a particularly vulnerable position as there is a strong critique of many Roma responsible against the “Kashtalii” (the ones who don’t speak the language, from *kasht*, wood). He has to stick to the “technician” position and point out his commitment and hard work for the Roma whenever discussing with those who make a distinction between “the real Roma” and the Kashtalii. He is dark skinned and has an impeccable suit, all the details of his appearance, from postural attitudes to the objects that he carries with himself shows he is an official person. The way he describes the situation and the communities is predominantly from an outsider’s point of view. At our first meetings, I had the impression that we are both coming from far away, from a different world: he was constantly using the word “they” when referring to the Spoitori and accounted various non-compliant behaviours of the inhabitants of Obor. Only later I found out that he actually lives 300 meters away. His status as an employee is uncertain, as after openly campaigning for the former Mayor he had difficulties in gaining the trust of the new Mayor. A somehow similar story has NA, a school mediator that runs the Community Centre in Oborul Nou. He has a degree in social sciences and lives in a social housing neighbourhood that is far from Obor so, at first, he appeared to be an urban activist that works for a community on programme based projects. Initially not speaking the language he learned it and became a professor of Romani, a job that was later passed to his wife, a native speaker. We later learned that his father actually lives in Obor and that he used to be a leader of local Roma for a while. NP, an older and more politically experienced Roma expert has a different history: he was always a “Spoitor”, not only a native speaker of Romani but closely related to many of the inhabitants of Livada.

We have to notice that “Roma expert” here is a generic term, the function as such does exist. However, all our actors use the syntagm as a title. There is another school mediator, a Romanian men working with the Spoitori, excellent speaker of Romani as acknowledge by the community and a sanitary mediator that, in theory has to deal with the entire Roma population of the city estimated in between 5,000 to 10,000 inhabitants. They always use the words “them”, “they

don't understand", and patronising phrases like "no matter what you do for them they will still be discontent". People also have a clear distance, their position is judged with the words "they don't do what they are supposed to do" and "they don't provide". Despite the bellicose tone on both sides when it comes to concrete topics there is a very neat collaboration, the Roma experts are indispensable both to the City and to the inhabitants.

The Roma experts are indispensable both to the City and to the inhabitants. Their status as secondary political actors is a perfect match of the processes that turns the ethnic housing areas into ghettos and of that type of governance that pushes and then keeps the poor, the Roma and especially the poor Roma together in urban slums.

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